

BroilerNet Kick off meeting 27th-29th of September 2022

Location: World Trade Centre Almere Conference Centre, then Netherlands

Agenda 27 of September

- 12.00 Arrival lunch
- 13.15 Welcome
- Project overview
- Consortium agreement – Non-disclosure agreement – Money transfer
- 13.45 Getting the group together – Jessica Stokes
- 14.30 WP 1- 30 min
- 15.00 Coffee
- 15.15 Presentations of separate WPs (WP 2-6)
- WP2-4 10 min each
- WP5 - 10 min each
- WP6 – 20 min each
- 17.00 Wrapping up the day
- 19.00 Dinner at Leonardo Hotel Almere City Centre, the Bierfabrik restaurant

Agenda 28 of September

- 9.15 Introduction
- 9.30 Participatory project timeline development (including coffee)
- 11.30 Project resource allocation exercise
- 12.00 Sandwich lunch
- 12.45 Project resource allocation exercise (continued)
- 13.45 Coffee
- 14.00 Presentation of Johan Leenders – Broiler farm and experience of Operational groups in EIP-AGRI
- 15.00 Bus leaves for excursion

Excursion program Batavialand

21.30 Back at WTC Almere

Agenda 29 of September

9.15 Communication, Dissemination and exploitation

10.15 Presentation by Celine Choquer, EC

~10.45 Coffee

11.30 Reflections on the days

- Next actions
- Wrapping up

12.00 Close meeting after that Lunch and departure

BroilerNet Kick off meeting 27th of September

WTC Almere Conference Centre

Participant list

Table 1. Organisations, country and participants at the Kick off in the BroilerNet project

Short Name	Country	Attending
SLU	SE	Stefan Gunnarsson
		Torun Wallgren
ANSES	FR	--
CRPA	IT	Paolo Ferrari
FLI	DE	Julia Malchow
		Karin von Deylen
IRTA	ES	Natàlia Majó Masferrer
ELGO	EL	--
RAU	UK	Jessica Stokes
SGGW	PL	Monika Gębska
UNI-LJ	SI	Manja Zupan Šemrov
WR	NL	Ingrid de Jong
		Francesca Neijenhuis
		Jamie Kater
UHEL	FI	Eija Kaukonen
FMV	PT	Magda Aguiar Fontes
		João Cota
SFS	SE	Maria Donis
		Anna Silvera
GAL	FR	Pauline Loiseau
UNAIT	IT	Anna Concollato
BVH	DE	--
FAC	ES	Anna Toda
PINDOS	EL	Apostolos Patsias (Απόστολος Πατσιάς)
BPC	UK	--
PZZH	PL	Aneta Oleksy-Gębczyk
PERUTNINA	SI	--
ANCAVE	PT	Pedro Raposo Ribeiro
Teagasc	IE	Rebecca Tierney
SIPI	FI	Hanna Hamina
LVOF	NL	Johan Leenders

Welcome

Stefan Gunnarsson started the meeting and presented the agenda for the meeting days.

Project overview

Stefan gave an overview of the project and the project partners. The project consists of a total of 25 partners from 13 different countries (all countries in the BroilerNet consortium were represented at the kick off) (Tab. 2). In twelve of the countries, the partners consist of countries one research partner (university or research institute) and one industry stakeholder representative. Thereto, Ireland is represented by Teagasc. All organisations are considered as equal partners in the project. The project covers a large part of the EU but the results will also be available by countries outside of EU. That is a requirement of the European Commission. The challenges/themes is a way of structuring the project, not cutting out possible topics.

Table 2. Organisations in BroilerNet consortium

Partner No.	Participant Organisation Name	Short Name
1(Coord.)	Sveriges lantbruksuniversitet	SLU
2	Agence nationale de sécurité sanitaire de l'alimentation, de l'environnement et du travail	ANSES
3	Centro Ricerche Produzioni Animali	CRPA
4	Friedrich-Loeffler-Institut: Bundesforschungsinstitut für Tiergesundheit	FLI
5	Institut de Recerca i Tecnologia Agroalimentaries	IRTA
6	Ellinikos Georgikos Organismos - Dimitra	ELGO
7	Royal Agricultural University	RAU
8	Szkoła Główna Gospodarstwa Wiejskiego w Warszawie	SGGW
9	Univerza v Ljubljani	UL
10	Stichting Wageningen Research	WR
11	Helsingin Yliopisto	UH
12	Faculdade de medicina veterinaria	FMV
13	Svensk Fågel Service AB	SFS
14	Terrena Société Coopérative Agricole (Galliance)	TERRENA
15	Unione Nazionale Filiere Agroalimentari delle Carni e delle Uova	UNAIT
16	Bundesverband bäuerlicher Hähnchenerzeuger	BVH
17	Federació Avícola Catalana	FAC
18	Agrotikos Ptinotrofikos Synetairismos Ioanninon	PINDOS
19	British Poultry Council	BPC
20	Polski Związek Zrzeszeń Hodowców i Producentów Drobiu	PZZHiPD
21	PERUTNINA Ptuj Reja Perutnine Proizvodnja Krmil Perutninskega Mesa in Izdelkov Trgovina in Storitve	PERUT
22	Federação Portuguesa das Associações Avícolas	ANCAVE
23	Teagasc	Teagasc
24	Suomen Siipikarjasäätiön	SIIPi
25	Leenders Vennootschap Onder Firma	Lennders VOF

Figure 1. General project description

The project consists of six specific objectives;

1. To establish 12 national Broiler Innovation Networks (BINs) of broiler farmers, integrator companies, farmers' organisations, advisors, researchers and veterinarians to enhance national collaboration, enable information exchange, and collect innovative ideas and Good practices (GPs) between the different partners in each country.
2. To create three Thematic Expert Networks (TENS) at the European level bringing together supply chain integrator companies, etc. around the three key themes (*environmental sustainability, animal welfare and animal health management*). The TENS aim to collect innovative ideas and practices from the bins, perform cost benefit analysis and disseminate best practices.
3. To engage with existing and new broiler-focused EIP-AGRI Operational Groups (OGs) and enhance their impact.
4. To Identify and assess the most urgent needs of broiler farmers across the three key themes.
5. To collect and evaluate the feasibility of practice-ready research solution - and innovative good practices- that meet the urgent knowledge needs identified for each of the three key theme, including cost- benefit analysis.
6. To disseminate practice-ready research solution- and innovative good practices and enhance uptake and impact by developing multi-language user material and videos to deploy the knowledge reservoir and organising national road shows.

To ensure that we are working on the correct topic everyone has been able to share relevant topics before the application was sent in and the selection of topics will be continued during the project. The topics suggested directly from farmers or farmers' perspective is considered especially important. The challenges and the solutions should be possible to implement on farm level and the project should work to enhance uptake of good and best practice. This should also live on even after the projects in finished.

There was one question regarding conducting small experiments during the project. The project budget may allow small scale testing, but the budget is mainly allocated to working hours for invest time and collect data and not to make experiments. The main idea is to circulate ideas, and that identified practices that are implemented at one place could be implemented elsewhere,

There was a question if it was possible to employ a PhD student in the project. It is unlikely that there is enough money to employ a PhD student in the project. However, there is nothing against it.

Paolo discussed the obstacles that can occur when you want to collect innovation from farmers and the importance to convey what is the benefit of sharing of the farmer. For instance, it should be mentioned that the sharing of ideas could stimulate new ideas within the network. It is important to emphasise these advantages as during for example the formation of the BINs.

Consortium agreement

Stefan presented the current state of the consortium agreement (CA). Before finalised, the updated CA will need to be sent around for signatures. The background is that the original CA did not harmonise with national legislation in some cases, particularly which appeal court that should be used in case of conflicts. The new CA will be sent next week. The updated part will be highlighted, so that partners can easily identify the updates. Please sign the updated CA as soon as possible to enable financial disbursement.

Non-disclosure agreement

A Non-Disclosure agreement will be sent out for signature along with the distribution of the CA.

Money transfer

A form for your financial office will be sent out and should be returned filled in and signed along with the distribution of the CA. No money transfer will however be distributed before all partners have signed the CA. We aim to have the money transfer as soon as possible, no later than Christmas.

The project pays for the stay here in Almere, including the food and the excursion.

Getting the group together – Jessica Stokes

Jessica Stokes (RAU) presented a presentation exercise to facilitate for all participating partners to introduce themselves. The exercise took 45 minutes.

Presentations of Work packages (WP)

Each WP leader had time to introduce the WP for the participants. AS WP2, 3 and 4 have the same structure their presentation of these WPs were partly done in collaboration between the WP-leaders.

WP1 Broiler innovation networks at international and European level. Jessica Stokes

The WP1 relates to the project objectives through establishing 12 Broiler Innovation Networks (BINs). The BINs consist of people from the value chain or in the knowledge and information system. The aim is to harvest good practices (GP) that can be shared within the group and on EU-level. There should be one BIN in each project country. They could also consist of Broiler farmers in the relevant

broiler AKIs: advisors, educator institute, NGOs etc. as well as engaging existing networks. Mapping the broiler AKIs in each country that creates an infrastructure to ensure that we include and mobilise all relevant actors. The BINs will come together at least twice a year.

The main role of the Role of BINs is to identify and assess the most urgent needs/challenges. They collect good practices across each county related to identified challenges and organise BROILERNET championships. Within the BINS, there is also discussion and collectively learning to tackle the real day-to-day farm challenges of the network members. They also supply support the networks on national level to develop their ideas further through forming EIP-AGRI Operational groups (OG) and apply for EIP-AGRI funding.

There is also formation of TENs. The TENs level brings together supply chain integrator companies, farmers, organisations, advisors etc. around the three key themes. They include representatives from research, industry, producers' organisations, advisors, veterinarians etc. Their role is to identify European level priority challenges and provide research and practice-based knowledge on the state of the art to address these challenges. They also screen the good practices identified by the BINs.

Engage with existing new and created EIP-AGRI OG groups.

WP1 also train the Broiler network facilitators (BNFs). Overall, there should be facilitators in the project (one per industry partner). Their role is to facilitate the broiler network and mobilise different kinds of knowledge, creating dialogue, leading knowledge sharing, establish national level BINs, organise BIN meetings/workshops (2 per year) as well as identify urgent needs. According to the time line, there is a facilitation training in March, which is complemented with regular online catch up meetings. The final time line will be discussed later this meeting. They also have a Toolkit development: materials and tools GP evaluation tools for co-translation and co-creation of knowledge ready for dissemination to practice.

The following questions were discussed:

The facilitator training dates: The facilitation training aims to support the industry partner to facilitate harvesting innovators. Needs to be synchronized with the overall time line. According to several partners, it will be difficult to plan this before Christmas 2022 due to already full calendars.

Formation and facilitation of the TENs: it was suggested that the thematic WP leaders be the leaders of this

Involving OGs and link with other projects, will be discussed further later on this meeting.

Link with other projects:

When should the BINs be established and when should the first meeting be? The suggestion was that the facilitators should first be trained that they can facilitate the meeting of the BINs. It is possible to use existing networks for the BINs if they are considered useful, for example the Hennovation network. This should happen in month 1-9. In BovINE, there was not enough time to establish the BINs and have the BINs come up with the challenges during Y1. Therefore, the first challenges came from within the project. This was suggested also for BroilerNet to ensure the time line for year 1. However, if this is practiced, the challenges should come from the industry partners and not the scientific partners. The BINs could also be created before the facilitation training.

WP2 Environmental sustainability. Paolo Ferrari (CRPA)

All thematic WPs are set up the same way. There are three main steps; 1) Make an inventory of current and prospective thematic challenges in different production systems through bottom up

stakeholder based approached (through bins). 2) Compile science based and on-farm practice-based information on Good Practices (GP) to address the identified main thematic challenges. This comes also from the scientific and grey literature, which is also used for the thematic reports that are published each year. 3) Evaluate and report by the tool produced in WP1. The most innovative Best Practice every year are awarded in the BroilerNet championship as a way to link the award with the best of the good practices. During this championship there is a feasibility challenge including the economic cost. Most information will probably come from the real world and the experience from the farmers. Every year, there will be the same process. Identify challenges, find best practices, evaluate and find the championship.

Examples of challenges for the sustainability theme could be emissions of Green House Gases, dust, ammonia or antimicrobials, energy saving, reduction of water consumptions.

Every partner should contribute with challenges through the BINs. During the workshop tomorrow, different partners will be allocated to the different WPs.

There was a question regarding if there was a minimum of best practices to be collected and no such limit is set.

The definition of GP was discussed and it was concluded that all GP couldn't be translated into new contexts. Although some GP cannot be translated into other contexts, they might be adaptable to other circumstances. However, not all of the collected GP will be translatable to all countries, but may still be considered a GP in an individual country.

WP3 Animal welfare. Julia Malchow (FLI)

The objectives are the same as in WP2 and 4.

An example of a challenge in Animal welfare could be support natural behaviour such as resting, pecking or comfort behaviour. The challenges are to be defined for the BINs. Examples of challenges could also be perception of good animal welfare, role and use of natural light, control of microclimate, reducing injuries at catching, litter quality etc.

The challenges for animal welfare can also relate/ overlap to other WP, which means that the challenges should be discussed on beforehand to ensure a balanced workload between the WPs.

WP4 Animal health management. Natàlia Majó Masferrer (IRTA)

The objectives are the same as in WP2 and WP3.

Possible challenges for WP4 could be improving biosecurity measures and disease prevention, reducing antimicrobial use, investigating alternatives to antibiotics/coccidiostats, implementing different vaccination strategies, enhancing health management and understanding when treatment should be applied.

WP5 Cost-benefit analysis. Monika Gębska (SGGW)

The work of WP5 will be based on the other WP, and without the effort of the other WPs the work of WP5 cannot start. There are four deliverables and four milestones. There is no time for delay in order to meet the timeline.

There are four main objectives: to develop a methodology to conduct analysis. Then perform the cost benefit analysis on the GP. The same methodology will be applied on the different themes. In total, there will be six BP evaluated per year, and in total 24 over the course of the project. The same approach will be used for evaluation in all themes; therefore, we have to agree on how to do it and on which type of data that we need to do a good cost benefit analysis. That means that we need to use data that we can find in all different countries, in order to make fair comparisons. Only data on the best practices will be requested. The main part of the data will probably come from real prices and technical performance but some data might have to come from statistics dependent on what is available. In order to do estimations (if needed) we need to use expert opinions.

There is also a collaboration with Wageningen University and Peter van Horne that can assist with data and estimations.

WP6 Outreach and increasing impact. Ingrid de Jong (WR)

The main tasks of WP 6 are communication, dissemination and exploitation. We do the project promotion and branding as well as generating dissemination materials focusing on end users.

In WP6, there will also be outreach activities to increase the impact of BroilerNet, also for people outside the project, such as conferences, events and roadshows. There is a sustainability plan to ensure exploitation of the results also after the project has ended. In addition, the final project international conference is managed by WP6

It is the joint responsibility of all partners to facilitate communication, dissemination and exploitation of the project and thus information is needed to WP6 from all partners and WPs. WP6 will also often approach the different partners.

There is already social media linked to the project, such as LinkedIn: BroilerNet, Twitter: @broilernet web: BroilerNet.eu it will be in place in M3 (end of October).

On Thursday morning, there will be more time to discuss WP6.

Thereafter, Jessica introduced the task for tomorrow and Stefan ended the meeting for the day.

BROILERNET Kick off- Wednesday 28th of September

WTC Almere Conference Centre

Introduction

Stefan introduced the agenda of the day and made a recap of yesterday's activities.

After the kick off meeting, all information regarding the project and project partners will be shared with all partners through MS teams. MS teams will also allow communication through different channels to facilitate communication on different levels, such as the entire group or WP level etc.

Participatory project timeline development

Jessica led the project timeline development work. All WP leaders had been asked on beforehand to write all tasks, milestones and deliverables on post-its. All participants were asked to write down events on post-its. The post-its were then attached on a timeline and together we edited the timeline so that the tasks/milestones/deliverables/events lined up correctly. The months in the timeline (and in the proposal) indicate the deadline for the tasks and milestones. This means that it is OK to finish earlier than the stipulated month, but not later.

Month 1 of the project is August 1st 2022.

In the project, the WP leaders are facilitators, but all partners should know what is going on and what is expected from them, when, what and where. WP2, 3 and 4 are very alike and have the same tasks and deliverables. Therefore, they largely have the same programme/outline.

Month 1-6

WP1:

Facilitator training: the timing of the facilitator training was discussed. It was initially planned for M7. However, this will make it difficult to be able to identify the challenges in time to stick to the deadlines with the broiler championships. Some partners want to include it as soon as possible while other partners cannot manage to fit it to existing calendar before Christmas. From WP1s perspective, it is preferable to do the training in person to receive the best results. They have experience of doing this type of training many times and if they are doing it online it does not give the same results and entail to big compromises to the training. Other partners think that allowing the facilitators to participate online would ease the project and maybe allow for the facilitator training to happen earlier. The training was done digitally during the similar Bovine project. It was proposed that countries and partners that want to do it as in the proposal could do that. However, if it does not work out, the short list of challenges from the proposal might be used. Jessica brings this to the WP-leader Lisa.

WP3/4/5:

Identification of challenges innovation needs and best good practices: This was discussed as it is essential to complete this task early to reach the deadline of identifying champions. It was discussed

that this task should be moved as early as possible. However, the identification of challenges and innovation needs should be an interactive process and might there for not be possible before the BINs are formed. A shortlist of challenges for each theme was presented in the proposal; it was proposed that this shortlist was used to identify challenges for Y1. The risk for now is that it takes too long to identify challenges, which leaves only 2 months to collect good practices (GP). No decision was made regarding if to use the shortlist for year 1 or not.

WP6:

The WP 6 will also be discussed more thoroughly during the meeting on Thursday.

Build website: to be finished M3.

Build broiler knowledge hub: Although the hub is created already in the first 6 months, there is not yet anything to put in the hub as we have not yet collected good practices. We should however be mindful about how to design it, so please come with input to this task. Ingrid will talk to Lisa about the hub that was designed in the Farmbook project.

Press release: There was a suggestion to make a press release in English in order to launch the project. Each country could then translate the press release and publish it in the native language in order to increase the spread of the news.

Identify outreach event: this task starts in the beginning of the project and are then continuously done throughout the project. This task aims to identify events where we could join as a project and events that we create through the project. The events could also be linked to thematic transnational events for BINs (that are organised twice in M18 and 28, WP1). However, it was not stipulated in the application how many transnational BIN events that we should arrange. The number of meetings is however restricted by the budget and arranging more than two might be tight moneywise. Action for everyone: if you know of any national event, let WP6 know!

Create social media accounts: They are active already (LinkedIn, Facebook, Twitter)

WP7:

Project management, Data management plan etc. will be managed by Stefan.

Minutes of kick off meeting, are what you are currently reading.

External events/activities

EuroTier in Germany: we have the opportunity to present BroilerNet (Julia Malchow)
National poultry meeting at The Swedish National Veterinary Institute (SVA) at the 4-5th of October 2022 (Stefan Gunnarsson)

Month 6-12:

WP1:

The Broiler innovation networks (BIN) should be established in M6 and not M8 that is stipulated in the application.

Workshop on developing of tools for priority needs/challenges identification and GP evaluation tool is moved to M6 instead of M8 or in November 2022 to meet with timing of other tasks.

Second BIN meetings to discuss and harvest GP and collective learning is moved from M12 to M7 to fit the timeline as this should happen before the champions are identified. The BP should be collected and analysed around M9/10.

WP2/3/4:

The Literature review and database should be finished; this includes keyword selection and databases. Here input is needed from all partners to make sure that the correct keywords and databases are used. Both scientific and grey literature will be used. The information from this task will be used to create the scientific background in the thematic reports in the different WP.

The WP leaders are part of planning the BINs and TENs meetings along with WP1.

WP5:

Develop methodology for the cost benefit analysis: The methodology and guidelines for data collection should be ready. It will contain what economic parameters to collect and how to collect them (quickly and right) to enable easy data collection for all partners. There is just a short period between the deadline for the guideline preparation and the collection of economy data (2 M). To collect all needed data, farmers must be approached twice; first about good practices and if they are selected best practice also about economic aspects. This process will take time why it is important that the challenges are identified asap in M0-6. If needed, maybe Peter van Horne can give information about baseline on countries where baseline is missing.

There was a discussion regarding the selection of good practices and that it may be harder than the selection of challenges. For the first year, the shortlist of challenges presented in the application may be used to give more time to initiate the facilitator training, formation of BINs and subsequently have more time to identify GP.

It was not mentioned in the application who facilitates and coordinates the workshop with TEN facilitators. It was decided that the WP leaders should lead these tasks.

Developing and discussing championship with the WP leaders. Along with the finalisation of the evaluation tool.

Regular BIN catch up: This entails questions and learning between countries. In order to create an easy way for all partners to see what is ongoing and what has been done, it was suggested that there should be an excel sheet together with a calendar on MS Teams.

External events/activities:

There is a training for poultry producers in Poland in November. During this meeting, they could collect a first approach to collect challenges. In Germany, the same approach could be used during EuroTier.

Month 12-18

WP1:

2nd BIN meeting: To discuss and harvest GP and collective learning.

Facilitator training in January. Need input from BINs in month 8 (March)

Workshops for TENs needs to be moved to M8.

Development of feedback loops between BINs and TENs should be established. For the facilitators of the BINs, there are also refinement workshops (could be done online) that could be attached to the project meetings.

Formation and first meeting of the TENs. TENs facilitators could be the WP leaders of WP 2, 3, and 4. TENs should express their opinion of the best practices. They should be created before M10. They should be participating in M10. The TENs are needed in the process of the championships.

WP5:

Here we should have information about the best GP and start to provide cost benefit analysis on all three themes. This step is then repeated each year. There is a report that is a milestone in M22, which is public. It should only contain information about the champions from year 1 and not Year 2. In total, there are three reports during the project. The second report or the last report will therefore contain reports from two years instead of one.

WP6:

There is a communication plan to be updated every 6 months; this will be discussed more during tomorrow morning.

There is also a yearly dissemination and identification of GP. We will for example make project videos about the project.

Month 18-24

WP1:

Transnational event for BINs to share good practices. Suggested to be 2 events in total, we could move them if needed M18 &30

3rd BIN meeting (one every 6 months roughly)

Reflection workshop, together with the project meeting. Sharing what is going well, what can be done differently in the future?

In general, WP1 and the other WPs are not aligning well. WP1 should align and support as best as possible in the future.

WP5:

Broiler championship, M18 and M30. Talked about the pre-requisite tasks that need to feed in.

Collection of economic data, second round, keep going on the cycle. Then there is the second round of cost benefit analysis.

TENs meetings M9 (24, 40)

WP6:

Communication Dissemination Exploitation plan update

Project resource allocation exercise

Ingrid introduced the project resource allocation exercise. The purpose of the exercise is to provide a clearer division of implementation responsibilities across tasks among the partners. During the exercise, each WP leader was provided with a flip chart. On the flip chart, the different tasks and deliverables were presented. Each partner could then decide which WPs and tasks they want to participate in. Partners not participating in the meeting will also be allocated tasks, and some reallocation might be done in order to have an even distribution of partners in the different WPs.

Presentation of Johan Leenders – Broiler farm and experience of Operational groups in EIP-AGRI

Johan presented his farm and how he has worked in an Operational group funded by EIP-AGRI.

BROLERNET Kick-off Thursday 29th of September

WTC Almere Conference Centre

Grant management under Horizon Europe. Céline Choquer European commission (EC)

Céline Choquer gave a presentation about grant management under Horizon Europe context. It is under the key funding programme for research and innovation that runs until 2027. Our actions will contribute to governance models enabling sustainability. Research innovation programme is linked to other EU policies. In our call there were five proposals submitted, three was funded.

Celine is our main contact in REA. The channel of the contact in the project is mainly through Stefan. Financial officer: Charlotte Pont. Our contact in DG Agri is Patricia Lopez

Céline's role is to support and advice, follow up implementation, assess reports and deliverables, and launch interims and final payments. She also facilitates project outputs for policymaking and provide access to communication and dissemination.

Horizon Europe grant agreement (GA)

New from the 2020 programme is that there is a data sheet summary of the specific grant agreement.

Project participants, beneficiary partners sign the GA and have all rights and obligations. Associated partners cannot annotate money. All partners should provide information to the coordinator to financial report and the technical report.

Reporting and reviews: There are two different kinds of report: continuous reports (contact with coordinator) and periodic and final reporting (after month 18, 36 and 48).

There is 60 days to submit the report. As reports are sent in, they will be reviewed. After the review, there is a meeting where you present the work and the results. At the end of this project, the opinion of an expert doing the review triggers the final payment of the project.

Financial aspects: Keep records and supporting documents for at least 5 years. Records for personnel costs such as time sheets should be kept. It is possible to organize a webinar on the financial aspects for the project partners.

Amendments: Amendments of the project may not result in changes if they, if known before awarding the grant, would not have had an impact on the decision to award to the project. It is possible to have a flexibility to the project, as long it is not substantial. Reasons for delay must be reported to Celine.

Public deliverables will be published in the commission open database. We should obey open science and comply with statues ethical principles.

Subcontracts: You cannot subcontract another beneficiary

Outreach – communication: We make a difference between communication, dissemination and exploitation activities. Communication is about results and project, dissemination is results only and exploitation is the actual use of the results for scientific societal economic purpose or for policymaking.

Visibility for EU funding: The use of the EU flag is necessary in all communication and infrastructure of the project. It is possible to read more about communication on the online portal.

Celine emphasised the importance to interact and build on previous and ongoing projects. Share especially the BP with the AKI-channel and EU FarmBook. Take into consideration also the potential barriers such as language barriers and technical barriers that may decrease the use of the platform

Celine also reminded that the project should be as green as possible, which entails to minimize travels, promote gender balance etc.

Communication, Dissemination and exploitation

Ingrid presented the interactive exercise on communication, dissemination and exploitation of WP6. During the exercise, all participants have to engage in identifying stakeholders and means for communication dissemination and exploitation.

The outcome of the workshop will be described elsewhere.

Reflections made by participants

To round up the meeting, all partners had the possibility to reflect on the meetings during the kick off. Below are the mentioned reflections,

“Thank the organizers and participants for the good mood. It has been fun to work together!”

“The relationship with farmers that have good practices, one tricky question is privacy and intellectual rights. We need to find a way to comply with legislation and to check with farmers that they are OK with showing their name or names/privacy data and right to share their practices. In another project, we tried to do that but those who proposed a template, the template was too strict and they ended up not using it. We have to find a way to comply, but the template must be as simple as possible. We should think about it and have comply with legislation to find a good solution. It’s a way to not have problems in the end.”

“Thanks for the good organisation. I was most impressed with the interactive session the first day. We found out both theoretically and practically that we are very friendly.”

“ I am not yet really aware of all the industry partners of the project and what they do. It would be nice to find a way where they can present themselves during an event or so. Maybe that is something that we could gather on the platform, or on zoom? Perhaps it could also be a part of the website? Or if we could link to their websites”

“ I enjoyed the interactive sessions, they were very nice. I feel involved in the project and learned more what it is about”

“Many people are probably going to the same meetings, like EuroTier, maybe we can arrange a meeting at such an event as well”

Please share if you have more ideas or reflections!

Minutes prepared and reviewed by the participants.

Skara/Uppsala the 20th of October 2022.

Torun Wallgren, Secretary

Stefan Gunnarsson, coordinator

Signature page

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